

Role and Requirement of Students and Teachers in Quality Enhancement of Higher Education Institutions

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ABSTRACT

Enhancing quality and relevance of education has been the prime challenge for India since long back. Various strategies have been evolved to counter this challenge. After secondary education students are required to come out with comprehensive knowledge, excellent communication skills and competent enough to face the various challenges in this intricate and interdependent world. Quality is multifaceted concept and several strategies for quality assurance and management at individual and organisational level are required. Assistance and role of many stakeholders in this field can be exercised. These stakeholders play vital role for enhancing quality of education in Higher Education Institutes. Role of two stakeholder viz. students and teachers have been discussed in this paper. Sincere and loyal efforts on the part of students and teachers through their involvement in decision making, policy formulation, curriculum construction etc can bring metamorphosis in this field. Relationship of students with teachers is of paramount nature and remains forever. So, major part of responsibilities for enhancing the quality of education lies on the shoulder of these two stakeholders. Certain liabilities on the part of students and teachers, destined for some constructive outcome has been covered in this paper. Multi areas of students and teacher's participation, challenges faced by them and suggestions for inclusive developments in Higher Education Institutions are discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Stakeholder, Communication skills, Higher Education, Quality enhancement

1. Introduction

Quality and relevance of education has always been a

challenge for India. Multidimensional strategies have been implemented in higher educational institutions for the betterment of quality of education. Stakeholders play vital role in enhancing or decreasing the standard of education. So, sincere, dedicated and loyal efforts in positive direction must be exercised. Integral and indispensable parts of any educational institution be it students, teachers, administrative staff, media, govt. etc cannot shed responsibilities from their shoulders. So, everybody's involvement with positive attitude is imperative.

2. Role and Requirement of Students as stakeholder

A stakeholder is a person or a group who affect the quality of education in higher education institutions or are affected by it. Involvement of students is an inclusive concept and corporate enterprise. Students are basic partners who are in centre of interest of higher education institutions.

2.1 Ways and Areas of Students Participation

- Engagement of student's community in the process of curriculum construction through feedback mechanism would be highly essential for quality enhancement. Feedback can be received through questionnaire, interviewing students individually, opinions of selected representatives, suggestion boxes, emails etc.
- Meeting between students and head of the institutions can have multiple positive inferences. Suggestions of students can be sought on important issues like budget allocation for physical resources,

annual programme, procurements of infrastructure for laboratory and library etc. Suggestions given by the students may be discussed upon for implementation or rejection. Action plan on given suggestions may be worked upon.

- Participation of students may be ensured in decision making bodies of govt., management including curriculum.
- Working area of student's council can be enhanced to realise maximum involvement of students which can bring forth innovative ideas for better education.

2.2 Problems in Student's participation

There are lot many problems in ensuring student's useful participation in different activities of education institutions.

- Student's voice is not acknowledged genuinely in determining the nature and contents of courses. It is the teachers and management who decide this.
- Students are not given right to have the content of their choice.
- Teachers have narrow conception of student's participation.
- In feedback mechanism, questionnaire presented are not relevant to students. Like this students are not able to voice their suggestions which they want actually.
- Students are not comfortable to give their views on teacher's capability, way of teaching or knowledge of subject matter.
- Students are less interested in this process. They have the conception that no action will be initiated on the part of institution on their feedback.
- Student's voting rights are limited and not authorized to vote for like administrative and financial issues, concern staff appointment and curricula etc.
- Students are hard pressed to complete their study and reluctant to join institutional life.

2.3 Suggestions to Ensure Purposeful Involvement of students

- Training, motivation and awareness programmes

must be arranged for students to ensure maximum and effective involvement.

- Feedback on learning experiences of students should be received in first half of a semester. So that any discrepancy or limitation can be rectified in subsequent semesters to ensure quality.
- Student's feedback must be acknowledged on priority to establish a credible and transparent environment.
- Ratio of student's participation in decision making should be enhanced for maximum output.
- Student's representatives should be elected rather than appointed.

3. Role and requirement of Teacher as Stakeholder

It has been found that 10% Indian youth go to colleges. Percentage of students going to colleges in developed countries is 40-50%. According to available data two third of Indian universities are providing inferior education, while 90% of college in India are below average. Most of the institutions have become the factory of degree only. Teachers as well as students are running after providing or acquiring degree and not towards enhancing knowledge and wisdom. Attendance in colleges has dropped drastically and class room teaching is becoming only a ritual, to be followed mechanically.

Though it has been said that destiny of nation is shaped only in the classroom, very less importance is being given to classroom teaching. Level of teaching in Indian institutions is not matched with global quality standard. Teaching in India does not foster global competence and are not as per the expectations of employment sector. Contribution of teachers is viewed with immense importance to bring metamorphosis in the quality of higher education. This daunting task of teachers to improve the quality of education play crucial role. Teachers are trusted with to bring whole world in class. This entirely depends upon the potential and wisdom of teacher. This is the responsibility of the teachers to create interest in students about subjects. Teachers are bound to inspire serious as well as non-serious students to take interest in their respective subjects. Success of any institution depends upon competence and quality of teacher. How and what he/she teaches in the class? Quality education is not a close ended concept but it's a continuous process and teacher needs to update him or herself with latest

methods and technologies invented in this field.

- **Motivation**

Motivation is imperative whenever we undertake some task. Motivation is a boosting factor to execute assigned task enthusiastically. In the class, teacher acts as a motivational force to motivate students to take interest and think rationally on given task. Due to the motivation of teacher in the class, learning and conducive environment is created to have maximum output.

- **Skill Enhancement**

Skills are part and parcel of everybody's life. Without skills no one can excel in life and achieve desired goal. Skills plays crucial role in student's life. Skilled persons with huge calibre are solicited in employment sector everywhere. It is the responsibility of teacher to develop the skills of students, be it job skill or communication skills. This require teacher to be innovative, creative and entrepreneurial in approach to develop skills in students. These skills can be enhanced while establishing contacts with social organisations, industrial set up and networking with neighbourhood agencies.

- **Loyalty**

Loyalty and commitment on the part of teachers play crucial role in student's life. Teacher's dedication towards profession shapes the future of students and nation. Teacher's impact on the life of students is everlasting so a dedicated and committed teacher can bring metamorphosis in quality of higher education.

- **Education Imbued with Value**

Skills are not of much use if these are devoid of value. In the absence of suitable value system, skills are treated with less importance. Teacher should bear the responsibility to inculcate value system amongst students to get in right direction. India is a diverse country in term of geography, culture, religion and language. But despite of so many pluralities in country, appropriate core values like truth and righteousness can be imbibed with life. If students are made to confront values in early stage, subsequent time will be conducive for all round development of students. During gurukul time, students were taught value lessons of honesty, truthfulness, loyalty, sincerity, dedication, self-respect and discipline. But unfortunately present scenario of higher education is not in association with these core values. Value

educations give direction to life with satisfaction and enhance the quality of higher education.

- **Personality of Teacher**

Personality does not mean mere good appearance but much more than that. Personality is a combination of multiple traits one teacher should have. Teacher should be disciplined, having high calibre, thorough knowledge of subject matter, effective body language, excellent communication skills and permanent learners. Teaching and learning is a continuous process which last till one demise. So it is imperative on the part of teacher to be a permanent learner while teaching. Effective personality of teacher affects the teaching and learning in manifold ways thus enhances the quality of higher education.

- **Academic Developments**

It has been mentioned that learning is a lifelong process. Teachers play crucial role not only in enhancing the quality of education but also maintaining this. And it is possible only when teacher is also learning continuously. There is induction of new methods and invention of latest technology in education sphere. It is very much important for all teachers to acquaint themselves with latest technological tools used in education field and new methods of teaching. Effective teaching can be realised through two facts i.e. teachers are familiar with new inventions in the field of education and researchers know the area of problem faced by teacher and students in classroom interaction. Teachers should incessantly attend seminars and workshop organised by different agencies. Teachers should be well versed in using latest technological tools used for effective teaching and learning. Refreshers course should be attended by teachers to update and enhance their existing knowledge.

- **Self-Rating**

Teachers should self-evaluate their teaching to discern the deficiency and shortcoming in their teacher. This can be done through analysing the results of students and their grade. Self-evaluation play crucial role in enhancing quality of higher education.

- **Professional Liberty**

Teachers should have professional liberty in the class. Though certain methods have been suggested by higher authorities to be implemented in the classroom still they should not dictate the teachers to adopt the same. Teacher's professional liberty to do experiment with

genuine methods of instruction in the class enhances the quality of higher education. Because teachers know their students well and know the methods suitable for effective learning.

• Professional Morality

Teachers have been given the highest place in Indian society. Teacher is even greater than God as per Hindu belief system. So teachers must abide by the professional ethics and shun the corruption activities in this sacred profession. If teacher is sincere, honest and loyal, the same message he/she can give to their students with full conviction which is essential for quality education.

4. Conclusion

It can be concluded that students and teachers are two fundamental pillars of educational edifice. Role of these two stakeholders for enhancing quality of higher education is of paramount nature. Role of students in every decision making relevant to them and competent, efficient and innovative teacher can surely bring metamorphosis in quality of higher education. The aim of quality in higher education can be facilitated if these two stakeholders are given due attention to their feedback and requisite resources with infrastructure.

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